

LEAST MASTERED COMPETENCIES IN STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODULAR LEARNING MATERIAL

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Abstract. This study attempted to identify the least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability at Virgen Milagrosa Senior High School during the second semester of the school year 2020-2021 which served as a basis for the development of modular learning material. The descriptive-developmental method of research was employed in this study. The data gathering tools used were the third and fourth quarterly examination results, and the LRMSD evaluation instrument of DepEd to determine the level of acceptability of the proposed modular learning material. There is a need to improve the performance of Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. The Grade 11 learners manifested the least mastered competencies in Statistics and Probability. The proposed modular learning material can be used to address the least mastered competencies and improve the performance of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. The researcher recommends that teachers should evaluate the learners' level of performance to identify their least mastered competencies. They should be encouraged to develop modular learning material to improve the learner's performance. The proposed modular learning material developed in this study is recommended for use by Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. Similar studies should be conducted in other learning areas and other grade levels to improve learners' performance.

Keywords. Iloko Instructional Video, Performance Level, Least Mastered Competencies, Acceptability Level

1 Introduction

One of the sectors most shaken by the Covid-19 pandemic is education, affecting the lives of students in the country since March. Schools have closed and face-to-face classes have been suspended in an attempt to stop the spread of the coronavirus. The initial government response to impose community quarantine was to suspend classes in Luzon and later the rest of the country. For the remainder of the school year 2019-2020, students have started fulfilling academic requirements at home and teachers were required to provide assignments in place of classroom teaching. Several schools have adopted other modes of delivery such as online learning platforms.

To provide and sustain quality education despite lockdowns and community quarantine, the new normal has to be taken into consideration. As President Rodrigo Duterte had stated he would not allow face-to-face classes in the absence of any vaccine against COVID-19, the Department of Education (DepEd) and stakeholders developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) school year 2020-2021 to ensure continuing education. The BE-LCP is a package of education interventions that will enable students to continue learning and teachers to deliver instruction amid the COVID-19 threat.

The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-CLP) provides several learning delivery modalities that are being adopted by different schools in the country. These are face-to-face learning, distance learning (with three types: modular distance learning, online distance learning, and television/radio-based instruction), blended learning, and homeschooling. Schools can adopt one or a combination of these modes, depending on the COVID-19 restrictions as well as the context of the learners in the school or locality.

Education in the new normal is a challenging task in the Philippines in an attempt to push through education amidst the deadly pandemic caused by COVID-19. The Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) adopted and implemented the flexible model of blended learning despite many oppositions because of the risk of opening classes due to the virus. The different learning modalities are the following: Modular (Printed), Modular (Digitized), Online, Educational TV, Radio-Based Instruction, Home Schooling, and Blended Learning. For the cities where modern living is adopted and learners have the privilege of having an internet connection at home, Online learning is implemented especially for the high schools and colleges but for those living in rural areas or provinces where internet connection is

available for only a few, modular distance learning is implemented. Modular distance learning is the use of modules made by teachers with different tasks and learning activities based on essential learning competencies (Anzaldo 2021).

Modular learning is playing a significant part in the “new normal” of education in most schools, but as the following experiences in some households show, mothers and children are struggling through many difficulties in this mode of education. Learners are allowed to answer directly on them. The modules, along with activity sheets and other requirements, are submitted by the parents or guardians every Friday to their children’s teachers who then distribute the subsequent modules for the next week.

There are various strategies employed in teaching Mathematics one of which is the use of modules. The use of modules in instruction helps in promoting self-directed learning among learners. Self-directed learning emphasizes the responsibility of the learners as owners and managers of their learning and that learners have a greater awareness of their responsibility in making learning meaningful and monitoring themselves. The role of the teacher in self-directed learning is as a facilitator rather than a content transmitter with the assistance of instructional tools.

Learning during these trying times has brought different challenges to both educational institutions and learners and their families. Learning is seen as an opportunity for everyone. Rave et al., (2020) stressed that modular learning is the most popular type of Distance Learning. In the Philippines, this learning modality is currently used by all public schools because according to a survey conducted by the Department of Education (DepEd), learning through printed and digital modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method of parents with children who are enrolled this academic year (Bernardo, J). This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning.

The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners. The learners may ask assistance from the teacher via e-mail, telephone, text message/instant messaging among others. Where possible, the teacher shall do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance in the different subject areas of the curriculum. At the Senior High School level, the subjects taken by Grade 11 learners are Statistics and Probability.

Teaching Statistics and Probability is a challenging role for Mathematics teachers. Studies show that learners experience difficulties in learning the subject which leads them to have below-average performance in Mathematics. Individual factors such as interest and readiness to learn are presented in various literatures. Factors associated with teachers have also been found in studies across the globe. These teacher factors include teaching strategies and approaches, inadequate teaching materials, teacher content knowledge, and classroom management. Despite initiatives on the use of different approaches in teaching this subject, reports on the performance of learners are still below the average competencies. With this, it is necessary to go back to the basics and teach learners the step-by-step procedure before letting them experience unfamiliar technologies.

The researcher a Mathematics teacher, had observed that learners find difficulty in understanding the concepts and operations in Statistics and Probability which is assigned to them. Realizing the importance of supplementary instructional materials to ensure mastery of the lesson among the learners and fully aware of the importance of Mathematics in this modern society, this study intended to propose modular learning materials for Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability.

Based on the aforementioned ideas and concepts, there was a need to conduct this study, which focused on the preparation of modular learning materials for Grade 11 learners because the researcher wants to address the least mastered competencies of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability.

2 Review of Related Literature

The previous investigations conducted by several researchers have similarities and differences with the present study. The related studies discussed in this chapter enriched the researcher’s knowledge and helped to provide direction for the present study. Although the foreign and local studies deal with various topics, the materials contributed a lot to the present research work, particularly on the aspect of research methodology, and the use of modules as a learning material.

The study of Nardo (2017), and Lim (2016) primarily dealt with modules as means of self-instructional materials which come as self-learning kits and are focused on interaction-centered activities. Similarly, this study developed and proposed a modular learning material based on the least mastered competencies of learners. Likewise, the researcher was guided by the findings in the study of Columbano (2019) since it is related to the present study as it focuses on the development and validation of Statistics and Probability modules to improve student performance in mathematics.

The studies of Lim (2016) and Aquino (2018) are similar to the present study because they involved the use of modules in teaching Mathematics subject in college. Likewise, the researcher aimed to develop modules in Mathematics such as Statistics and Probability to address the least mastered competencies of learners. The present study differs from the previous studies because the developed modules are intended for Grade 11 senior high school students. The researcher was guided by these gathered related studies to develop modular learning materials that are suited to the learners. The researcher's study attempted to identify the least mastered competencies in statistics and probability as the basis for the development of self-learning modules for use by Grade 11 learners.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. It is descriptive because the researcher was involved analysis of the third and fourth quarterly examination results during the school year 2020 – 2021 to determine the level of performance of the Grade 11 learners and to identify their least mastered competencies in Statistics and Probability. This study is also developmental because the researcher developed and proposed modular learning materials for Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability based on their least mastered competencies as revealed by the third and fourth quarterly examination results.

3.2 Sources of Data

The third and fourth quarterly examination results were used by the researcher in determining the level of performance and in identifying the least mastered competencies of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. The identified least mastered competencies served as the bases in the preparation and development of the modular learning material in Statistics and Probability.

The self-learning modular lessons included in the proposed modular learning materials were evaluated by Mathematics teachers handling Statistics and Probability, and the senior high school coordinators from nine selected private secondary school programs offering Senior High Schools in the San Carlos City Division. Table 1 reflects the frequency distribution of Mathematics teachers handling Statistics and Probability and senior high school coordinators who served as evaluators. The results of the evaluation were used to determine the level of acceptability of the proposed modular learning material.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the level of performance of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability, the third and fourth quarterly examination results were used by the researcher. The mean percentage score (MPS) for each quarterly examination was computed, then the average MPS was obtained. This was used to describe the learners' level of performance per the scale prescribed by DepEd.

The least mastered competencies of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability were determined by conducting an item analysis of the third and fourth quarterly examination results. The percentage of correct response (PCR) was used to identify the least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners. The results of the itemized analysis were described using the DepEd-prescribed level of Mastery Scale.

To determine the level of acceptability of the proposed modular learning material, Average Weighted Mean (AWM) was used. Results were interpreted using a 4-point scale.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Performance of Grade 11 Learners in Statistics and Probability in the Third and Fourth Quarterly Examinations

Table 2 shows the third and fourth quarterly examination results in terms of the mean percentage scores. The learners obtained MPS of 52.75 and 57.71 in the third and fourth quarterly examinations respectively. The average MPS of 55.23 during that semester was way below the prescribed mastery level of 75% by the Department of Education.

Table 2. Third and Fourth Quarterly Examination Results
Second Semester, 2020-2021

Virgen Milagrosa Senior High School	3 RD Quarterly Examination	4 th Quarterly Examination	Average MPS	Descriptive Equivalent
MPS	52.75	57.71	55.23	Average Mastery

It could be deduced that there is a need to enhance the performance of the Grade 11 learners. It could be inferred further that there is a need for an intervention to help the learners improve their level of performance.

4.2 Least Mastered Competencies of the Grade 11 Learners in Statistics and Probability

Table 3. Identified Least Mastered Competencies of the Grade 11 Learners in Statistics and Probability Based on Third and Fourth Quarterly Examination Results

Competencies	Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Illustrates a random variable (discrete and continuous).	56	Not Mastered
2. distinguishes between a discrete and a continuous random variable.	60	Not Yet Mastered
3. finds the possible values of a random variable	63	Not Yet Mastered
4. illustrates a probability distribution for a discrete random variable and its properties	60	Not Yet Mastered
5. computes probabilities corresponding to a given random variable.	50	Not Mastered
6. Illustrates the mean and variance of a discrete random variable.	65	Not Yet Mastered
7. calculates the mean and the variance of a discrete random variable	43	Not Mastered
8. interprets the mean and the variance of a discrete random variable.	45	Not Mastered
9. solves problems involving mean and variance of probability distributions.	50	Not Mastered
10. illustrates a normal random variable and its characteristics.	59	Not Mastered
11. identifies regions under the normal curve corresponding to different standard normal values	57	Not Mastered
12. converts a normal random variable to a standard normal variable and vice versa	59	Not Mastered
13. computes probabilities and percentiles using the standard normal table.	64	Not Yet Mastered
14. illustrates random sampling.	64	Not Yet Mastered
15. distinguishes between parameter and statistic.	59	Not Mastered

Table 3 reveals the identified least mastered competencies based on the computed PCR which are below 75% and described as "Not Yet Mastered" or "Not Mastered". Looking closely at Table 3, the learners encountered learning difficulties in 15 learning competencies based on the third and fourth quarterly examination results. It could be noted that the learners manifested "not mastered" in 9 learning competencies as shown by the computed percentage of correct response (PCR).

On the other hand, the Grade 11 learners exhibited “not yet mastered” on the 6 competencies as shown in Table 3 based on the computed percentage of correct responses which are all lower than the prescribed 75% mastery level set by the Department of Education. Based on the results, the 15 least mastered competencies by the learners became the basis for the development of modular learning material in Statistics and Probability.

4.3 Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Modular Learning Material in Statistics and Probability

Table 4A reflects the results of the evaluation made by the Mathematics teachers on the level of acceptability of the proposed modular learning material in terms of the three factors or main indicators given in the LRMS rating sheet. As to “Content”, it could be gleaned from the same table that the teacher-respondents rated the modular learning material as “highly acceptable” as shown by the average weighted mean of 3.85. In terms of “Format” and “Presentation and Organization” the rating given by the teacher-evaluators is 3.82 AWM and 3.83 AWM respectively, both equivalent to “highly acceptable”. It could be noted that the teacher-respondents rated all the indicators under each criterion as “highly acceptable”.

Table 4. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Modular Learning Material as Evaluated by the Mathematics Teachers
N=16

Factor 1: Content	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Content is suitable to student’s level of development.	3.88	HA
2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	3.88	HA
3. Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving, etc.	3.88	HA
4. Material is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial and gender biases and prejudices.	3.88	HA
5. Material has the potential to arouse interest of target reader.	3.81	HA
6. Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are of concerns.	3.75	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.85	HA
Factor 2: Format		
1. Prints		
1.1 Size of paper is appropriate to intended user.	3.88	HA
1.2 Spaces between letters and words facilitate understanding.	3.75	HA
1.3 Font is easy to read.	3.94	HA
1.4 Printing is of good quality (i.e., no broken letters, even density, correct alignment, properly placed screen registration).	3.75	HA
2. Illustrations		
2.1 Simple and easily recognizable .	3.81	HA
2.2 Clarify and supplement the text.	3.94	HA
2.3 Properly labelled or captioned (if applicable).	3.88	HA
2.4 Realistic/ appropriate colors.	3.81	HA
2.5 Attractive and appealing.	3.75	HA
2.6 Culturally relevant .	3.81	HA
3. Design and Layout		
3.1 Attractive and pleasing to look at.	3.75	HA
3.2 Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader).	3.88	HA
3.3 Adequate illustration in relation to the text.	3.81	HA
3.4 Harmonious blending of elements (e.g., illustration and text).	3.81	HA
4. Paper and Binding		
4.1 Paper used contributes to easy reading.	3.81	HA
4.2 Durable binding withstand frequent use.	3.75	HA
5. Size and Weight Resource		
5.1 Easy to handle .	3.81	HA
5.2 Relatively light .	3.75	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.82	HA
Factor 3: Presentation and Organization		
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable.	3.88	HA
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas.	3.88	HA
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader’s likely to experience and level of understanding .	3.88	HA
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader.	3.81	HA
5. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target reader.	3.69	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.83	HA
Over-all Average Weighted Mean (OAWM)	3.83	HA

Based on the results of the evaluation made by the Mathematics teachers, it can be deduced that the proposed modular learning material intended to address the least mastered competencies of the learners could be effectively used as supplementary material in Statistics and Probability.

According to Charles (2021), the Modular approach to teaching mathematics for particular topics has been known to be an efficient and reliable tool for assisting learners in developing mathematics among themselves. He also stated that the modular approach is a conscience package associated with one specific subject efficiently, allowing the learner to distinguish the specific goals, select materials and methods, and assess his progress. This gives distance learners, as well as the learners, the most adaptability and allows them to develop initiative and responsibility

4.4 Evaluation of the Senior High School Coordinators

Table 4B. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Modular Learning Materials as Evaluated by the Senior High School Coordinators
N=8

Factor 1: Content	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Content is suitable to student's level of development.	3.88	HA
2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	3.88	HA
3. Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving, etc.	3.88	HA
4. Material is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial and gender biases and prejudices.	4.00	HA
5. Material has the potential to arouse interest of target reader.	3.88	HA
6. Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are of concerns.	3.88	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.90	HA
Factor 2: Format		
1. Prints		
1.1 Size of paper is appropriate to intended user.	3.75	HA
1.2 Spaces between letters and words facilitate understanding.	3.75	HA
1.3 Font is easy to read.	4.00	HA
1.4 Printing is of good quality (i.e., no broken letters, even density, correct alignment, properly placed screen registration).	3.88	HA
2. Illustrations		
2.1 Simple and easily recognizable .	4.00	HA
2.2 Clarify and supplement the text.	4.00	HA
2.3 Properly labelled or captioned (if applicable).	3.75	HA
2.4 Realistic/ appropriate colors.	3.75	HA
2.5 Attractive and appealing.	4.00	HA
2.6 Culturally relevant .	3.75	HA
3. Design and Layout		
3.1 Attractive and pleasing to look at.	3.88	HA
3.2 Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader).	4.00	HA
3.3 Adequate illustration in relation to the text.	4.00	HA
3.4 Harmonious blending of elements (e.g., illustration and text).	4.00	HA
4. Paper and Binding		
4.1 Paper used contributes to easy reading.	3.88	HA
4.2 Durable binding withstand frequent use.	4.00	HA
5. Size and Weight Resource		
5.1 Easy to handle .	3.88	HA
5.2 Relatively light .	3.63	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.88	HA
Factor 3: Presentation and Organization		
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable.	3.88	HA
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas.	4.00	HA
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader's likely to experience and level of understanding .	3.75	HA
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader.	3.88	HA
5. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target reader.	4.00	HA
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.90	HA
Over-all Average Weighted Mean (OAWM)	3.89	HA

The senior high school coordinators of eight private schools of the San Carlos City Division evaluated the proposed modular learning material in Statistics and Probability using the same set of criteria used by the Mathematics teachers. Table 4B reveals the results of the evaluation by the HS coordinator – respondents. It could be seen from the table that; the private senior high school coordinators rated the modular learning material as “highly acceptable” in terms of all the criteria used for evaluation. The computed overall average weighted mean is 3.89 which is equivalent to “highly acceptable”.

Based on the results, it can be inferred that the proposed modular learning material is appropriate for the use of Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. According to Lim (2016), the use of modules in teaching Mathematics is an effective teaching approach in the sense that it helps the students learn concepts in mathematics without cramming to keep up with the pacing of the teacher. The use of modules in teaching particularly concepts in Math is also useful for the learners in developing their study habits.

4.5 Summary of Evaluation of the Proposed Modular Learning Materials

The results of the evaluation made by the Mathematics teachers and senior high school coordinators on the level of acceptability of the proposed modular learning material are summarized in Table 5.

As reflected in the table, the Mathematics teachers rated the proposed modular learning material with an overall AWM of 3.83 equivalent to “highly acceptable”. Likewise, the Senior High School Coordinators gave an overall AWM rating of 3.89 which is also “highly acceptable”. As a whole, the computed general OAWM is 3.86, described as “highly acceptable”.

The results imply that the proposed modular learning material could be used as intervention material to address the least mastered competencies of Grade 11 learners and thereby improve their level of performance in Statistics and Probability.

Table 5. Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Modular Learning Materials
 N=24

Evaluators	Factors	AWM	DE
Mathematics Teachers	Content	3.85	Highly Acceptable
	Format	3.82	Highly Acceptable
	Presentation and Organization	3.83	Highly Acceptable
	OAWM	3.83	Highly Acceptable
Senior High School Coordinator	Content	3.90	Highly Acceptable
	Format	3.88	Highly Acceptable
	Presentation and Organization	3.90	Highly Acceptable
	OAWM	3.89	Highly Acceptable
General OAWM		3.86	Highly Acceptable

Based on these results, it could be deduced that the proposed modular learning materials could be effective instructional materials in addressing the least mastered competencies of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. The researcher strongly believes that the proposed modular learning materials for Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability could enhance the performance of the Grade 11 learners.

The findings of this study are parallel to the findings of Ferrer 2017 et.al that Mathematics teachers should design supplementary instructional material to address the least mastered competencies of the learners. Likewise, the Multiple Intelligence Theory of Dr. Gardner stresses the process of logical problems and equations is logico-mathematical intelligence. It does not require verbal articulation, for we can churn a complex problem in our mind, only to articulate it loud once the problem has been solved.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the descriptive analysis of the gathered data, the following are the salient findings of the study. The third and fourth quarterly examination results revealed that the mean percentage scores obtained by the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability are 52.75 and 57.71. The average MPS of 52.23 obtained by the learners is equivalent to the "Average Mastery level. The learners encountered learning difficulties in 15 learning competencies based on the third and fourth quarterly examination results. The Mathematics teachers from the private secondary schools in San Carlos City, Division rated the proposed modular learning material in Statistics and Probability as "highly acceptable" with an overall average weighted mean of 3.83. Similarly, the private senior high school coordinators rated the proposed modular learning material in Statistics and Probability as "highly acceptable" with an average weighted mean of 3.89. The general OAWM rating given by the two groups of evaluators is 3.86 described as "highly acceptable".

Given the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. There is a need to improve the performance of Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability. The Grade 11 learners manifested the least mastered competencies in Statistics and Probability. The proposed modular learning material can be used to address the least mastered competencies and improve the performance of the Grade 11 learners in Statistics and Probability.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for a possible course of action. Teachers should evaluate the learners' level of performance to identify their least mastered competencies. Teachers should develop modular learning material to improve the learner's performance. Teachers should encourage to development of modular learning material to improve learners' performance. The proposed modular learning material should be recommended for the use of Grade 11 learners as additional instructional material for better learning outcomes. Similar studies should be conducted in other learning areas and other grade levels to improve learners' performance.

References

- Anzaldo Geraldine D. 2021 "Modular Distance Learning in the New Normal Education Amidst COVID-19" Talisay Elementary School, Talisay Calatagan, Batangas, Philippines.
- Lim, Edgar Julius (2016) "Effectiveness of Modular Instruction in Word Problem Solving of BEED Students" Unpublished Master's Thesis, Eastern Samar State University
- Nardo, Theresa Ma B. 2017. "Modular Instruction Enhances Learner Autonomy." Tarlac Agricultural University, Camiling, Tarlac
- Rave, Y., Dangle, P., & Sumaoang, J." The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Secondary Public Schools". 2020